

Optimizing Dragonfly Algorithm using Ant Lion Algorithm for Solving Complex Numerical Optimization Problems

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Abstract:

Optimization algorithms play a key role in solving complex computational problems across various disciplines. In this paper, we introduce a new hybrid model that integrates the Dragonfly Algorithm (DA) and the Ant Lion Optimizer (ALO) for optimization performance enhancement. The new hybrid model integrates the exploration ability of DA and the exploitation ability of ALO with the expectation of better convergence and optimal solutions. We applied the model to optimize 23 benchmarking functions, and the results indicate that the hybrid model is better than the traditional algorithm approach in generating smaller errors and scores in the area of optimization. The study indicates that the proposed hybrid model offers a feasible solution to solving high-dimensional optimization problems.

Keywords:

Dragonfly Algorithm (DA), Hybridization, Benchmark, Exploration, Exploitation

Introduction:-

Optimization is a basic mechanism for addressing complicated problems in the areas of science, engineering, and artificial intelligence. Although metaheuristic algorithms have proven highly effective in dealing with vast search spaces, individual algorithms tend to experience problems with premature convergence or poor exploitation. This paper presents a hybrid methodology that blends the strengths of the Dragonfly Algorithm (DA)[16] and the

Ant Lion Optimizer (ALO)[17] to facilitate a more uniformly distributed and effective search process. By utilizing the exploratory ability of DA and the enhanced exploitation capabilities of ALO, our proposed model optimizes both convergence rate and solution precision. The hybrid algorithm was evaluated on 23 benchmark functions, and the results were always superior to those of the individual DA and ALO, hence indicating an enhancement in optimization efficiency and stability. These findings imply that hybrid metaheuristic methodologies may be an effective substitute for addressing complicated optimization problems.

Literature Review:-

Fig1: Classification of Algorithms

Tabel 1: Publication Details
Flowchart:- [16][17]

$F_8(S) = \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} [100(S_{m+1} - S_m^2)^2 + (S_m - 1)^2]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-38, 38]	0
$F_9(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n [(S_m + 0.5)^2]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0
$F_{10}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n m S_m^2 + \text{random} [0,1]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-1.28, 1.28]	0
$F_{11}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n S_m - S_m \sin(\sqrt{ S_m })$	(10,30,50,100)	[-500,500]	-418.98295
$F_{12}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n [S_m^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi S_m) + 10]$	(10,30,50,100)	[-5,12.5,12]	0
$F_{13}(S) = -20 \exp(-0.2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{m=1}^n S_m}) - \exp(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{m=1}^n \cos(2\pi S_m) + 20 + d)$	(10,30,50,100)	[-32,32]	0
$F_{14}(S) = 1 + \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{m}{4000} - \prod_{m=1}^n \cos \frac{3\pi m}{2500}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-600, 600]	0
$F_{15}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n [10 \sin(\pi r_m) + \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} (r_m - 1)^2 [1 + 10 \sin^2(\pi r_{m+1}) + (r_m - 1)^2] + \sum_{m=1}^n u(S_m, 10, 100, 4)]$ $r_m = 1 + \frac{3m-1}{4}$ $u(S_m, b, x, i) = \begin{cases} x(S_m - b)^i & S_m > b \\ 0 & -b < S_m < b \\ x(-S_m - b)^i & S_m < -b \end{cases}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-50,50]	0
$F_{16}(S) = 0.1 \{ \sin^2(3\pi S_m) + \sum_{m=1}^n (S_m - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2(3\pi S_m + 1)] + (x_2 - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2(2\pi S_2)] \}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-50,50]	0
$F_{17}(S) = \frac{1}{1000} + \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{S_m}{1 + \sum_{m=1}^n (S_m - b_m)^2}$	2	[-65.536, 65.536]	1
$F_{18}(S) = \sum_{m=1}^{11} [b_m \frac{S_m(a_m + m S_m)}{a_m^2 + m S_m^2}]^2$	4	[-5, 5]	0.00030
$F_{19}(S) = 45 S_1^2 - 2.1 S_1^4 + \frac{1}{5} S_1^5 + S_1 S_2 - 4 S_2^2 + 4 S_2^3$	2	[-5, 5]	-1.0316
$F_{20}(S) = (S_2 - \frac{1}{5} S_1^2 + \frac{1}{5} S_1 - 6)^2 + 10(l - \frac{1}{5}) \cos S_1 + 10$	2	[-5, 5]	0.398
$F_{21}(S) = [l + (S_1 - S_2 + 1)^2 (19 - 14 S_1 + 3 S_1^2 - 14 S_1 + 6 S_1 S_2 + 3 S_2^2)] \times [30 + (2 S_1 - 3 S_2) (18 - 32 S_1 - 12 S_1^2 + 48 S_1 - 36 S_1 S_2 + 27 S_2^2)]$	2	[-2,2]	3
$F_{22}(S) = - \sum_{m=1}^n d_m \exp(-\sum_{m=1}^n S_m (S_m - q_{mm})^2)$	3	[1, 3]	-3.32
$F_{23}(S) = - \sum_{m=1}^n d_m \exp(-\sum_{m=1}^n S_m (S_m - q_{mm})^2)$	6	[0, 1]	-3.32
$F_{24}(S) = - \sum_{m=1}^n [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0,10]	-10.1532
$F_{25}(S) = - \sum_{m=1}^n [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0, 10]	-10.4028
$F_{26}(S) = - \sum_{m=1}^n [(S - b_m)(S - b_m)^2 + d_m]^2$	4	[0, 10]	-10.5363

Benchmark Function:-

Table 2: Standard UM benchmark functions				
Functions	Dimensions	Range	f_{min}	
$F_1(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n S_m^2$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0	
$F_2(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n S_m + \prod_{m=1}^n S_m $	(10,30,50,100)	[-10, 10]	0	
$F_3(S) = \sum_{m=1}^n (\sum_{k=1}^m S_k)^2$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0	
$F_4(S) = \max_m \{ S_m , 1 \leq m \leq n \}$	(10,30,50,100)	[-100, 100]	0	

Sr.no	Algorithm	Author Name
1	Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)	Dorigo & Gambardella Et al. (1997)
2	Artificial Bee Colony (ABC)	Karaboga Et al. (2005)
3	Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO)	Simon Et al. (2008)
4	Evolution Strategy (ES)	Rechenberg Et al. (1973)
5	Electromagnetic Optimization (EO)	Birbil & Fang Et al. (2003)
6	Black Hole Algorithm (BHA)	Hatamlou Et al. (2013)
7	Social Spider Optimization (SSO)	Cuevas, Cienfuegos, Zaldívar Et al. (2013)
8	Soccer League Competition (SLC)	Moosavian & Gholipour Et al.(2015)

Search Space:-

Results & Discussions:-

Function	Original Algorithm Value	Hybrid Algorithm Value
F1	0.010844	0.17057
F2	0.41577	0.17384
F3	16.3224	3.8555
F4	5.0088	0.80819
F5	9.4514	9.5206
F6	3.8895	0.18766
F7	0.039007	0.015949
F8	-2491.2016	-3221.5408
F9	9.0597	8.0225
F10	3.9508	1.7239
F11	0.33914	0.72508
F12	0.65975	0.54286
F13	0.21484	0.20924
F14	0.998	0.998
F15	0.0016554	0.00062231

F16	-1.0316	0
F17	0.39789	0.39789
F18	3	3
F19	-3.8628	-3.8628
F20	-3.322	3.1801
F21	-10.1532	10.1526
F22	-10.4029	10.4027
F23	-2.8066	10.5334

From above table, conclude that hybrid DA-ALO giving more relevant and optimize value as compared to original algorithm. Some values are remained unchanged and some are showing fluctuation in values. Results of hybrid DA-ALO are impressive. Function such as F2, F3, F4, F6, F7, F8, F9, F10, F12, F13, F15 and F23 shows the enhancement in value.

Conclusion:-

This research improves the performance of DragonFly Algorithm using hybridization approach of (DA+ALO), The hybrid algorithm being tested on 23 benchmark functions out of which 12 functions provide a best optimal value compared to the original Algorithm which demonstrating an improvement in DragonFly Algorithm performance.

References:-

[1] W. Y. Lin, "A novel 3D fruit fly optimization algorithm and its applications in economics," Neural Comput. Appl., 2016, doi: 10.1007/s00521-015-1942-8.

[2] Y. Cheng, S. Zhao, B. Cheng, S. Hou, Y. Shi, and J. Chen, "Modeling and optimization for collaborative business process towards IoT applications," Mob. Inf. Syst., 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/9174568.

[3] X. Wang, T. M. Choi, H. Liu, and X. Yue, "A novel hybrid ant colony optimization algorithm for emergency transportation problems during post-disaster scenarios," IEEE Trans. Syst. Man, Cybern. Syst., 2018, doi: 10.1109/TSMC.2016.2606440.

[4] I. E. Grossmann, Global Optimization in Engineering Design (Nonconvex

Optimization and Its Applications), vol. 9. 1996.

[5] R. V. Rao and G. G. Waghmare, "A new optimization algorithm for solving complex constrained design optimization problems," vol. 0273, no. April, 2016, doi: 10.1080/0305215X.2016.1164855.

[6] E.-S. M. El-Kenawy, M. M. Eid, M. Saber, and A. Ibrahim, "MbGWO-SFS: Modified Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer Based on Stochastic Fractal Search for Feature Selection," IEEE Access, 2020, doi: 10.1109/access.2020.3001151.

[7] M. Nouri, A. Bekrar, A. Jemai, S. Niar, and A. C. Ammari, "An effective and distributed particle swarm optimization algorithm for flexible job-shop scheduling problem," J. Intell. Manuf., 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10845-015-1039-3.

[8] Y. Li, J. Wang, D. Zhao, G. Li, and C. Chen, "A two-stage approach for combined heat and power economic emission dispatch: Combining multi-objective optimization with integrated decision making," Energy, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.07.200.

[9] D. Yousri, T. S. Babu, and A. Fathy, "Recent methodology based Harris hawks optimizer for designing load frequency control incorporated in multi-interconnected renewable energy plants," Sustain. Energy, Grids Networks, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.segan.2020.100352.

[10] R. Al-Hajj and A. Assi, "Estimating solar irradiance using genetic programming technique and meteorological records," AIMS Energy, 2017, doi: 10.3934/energy.2017.5.798.

[11] R. Al-Hajj, A. Assi, and F. Batch, "An evolutionary computing approach for estimating global solar radiation," in 2016 IEEE International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications, ICRERA 2016, 2017. doi: 10.1109/ICRERA.2016.7884553.

[12] R. A. Meyers, "Classical and Nonclassical Optimization Methods Classical and Nonclassical Optimization Methods 1 Introduction 1 1.1 Local and Global Optimality 2 1.2 Problem Types 2

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<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/5c5c/908bb00a54439dcee50ec1ada6b735694a94.pdf>

[13] N. Steffan and G. T. Heydt, "Quadratic programming and related techniques for the calculation of locational marginal prices in distribution systems," in 2012 North American Power Symposium (NAPS), 2012, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/NAPS.2012.6336310.

[14] M. Mafarja et al., "Evolutionary Population Dynamics and Grasshopper Optimization approaches for feature selection problems," *Knowledge-Based Syst.*, vol. 145, pp. 25–45, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2017.12.037.

[15] A. A. Heidari, R. Ali Abbaspour, and A. Rezaee Jordehi, "An efficient chaotic water cycle algorithm for optimization tasks," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 57–85, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s00521-015-2037-2.

[16] Mirjalili, S. (2015). The Ant Lion Optimizer. *Advances in Engineering Software*, 83, 80–98. DOI: 10.1016/j.advengsoft.2015.01.010

[17] Mirjalili, S. (2016). Dragonfly algorithm: a new meta-heuristic optimization technique for solving single-objective, discrete, and multi-objective problems. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 27, 1053–1073. DOI: 10.1007/s00521-015-1920-1